

GraphQL Resources

fosseam.org

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GraphQL Resources by FOSSEA³M

The data sources for the API directory can be meaningfully divided into three groups. Each group serves a different purpose and targets a different audience, from learners and API explorers to professional API platform operators. Additionally, we have added some further links.

Learning & Practice APIs

Goal: Freely accessible GraphQL APIs suitable for education, training, and experimentation.

Criteria:

- No authentication required
- Free & publicly reachable
- GraphQL-only (or primarily GraphQL)
- Suitable for playground tools, tutorials, demo use

No.	Name	Count	Description
1	graphql-kit/graphql-apis	50+	Curated list of open GraphQL APIs with documentation and examples
2	StepZen Blog Article	10	Useful beginner-friendly overview with example APIs
3	Postman GraphQL API Network	10+	Preconfigured APIs for learning in Postman environments

Hubs & Catalogs

Goal: Aggregated sources with broader API coverage, often including both REST and GraphQL.

Criteria:

- Publicly accessible catalogs or lists
- Curated or indexed APIs
- May include authenticated or restricted APIs
- REST & GraphQL mixed

No.	Name	Count	Description
4	publicapis.io	1000+	Extensive API search engine with filters, tags, and structured entries
5	JSONAPI.co	900+	Thematically sorted open APIs – mostly REST, some GraphQL
6	APIs.guru GraphQL Interface	300+	OpenAPI catalog with GraphQL interface, primarily REST-focused

API Marketplaces & Portals

Goal: Access to commercial, production-grade, or enterprise-related API platforms.

Criteria:

- Authentication usually required
- Focus on API-as-a-Product, platform integration, monetization
- Often requires registration or API key
- High relevance for B2B and SaaS ecosystems

This classification enables targeted crawling, filtering, evaluation, and curation of APIs – based on maturity, licensing, and audience. More platforms can be added later (e.g. Azure API Center, Google Cloud APIs, Postman Public Workspaces, etc.). This table documents which major API marketplaces and developer portals are publicly browsable without a user account – meaning APIs can be discovered, browsed, or read about without having to log in.

No.	Provider	Count	Login Free?	Notes
1	SAP	100+	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	Fully browsable without login; API key required for Try-Out, but no account needed
2	Google	200+	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	Public API catalog with open documentation; Try-Out usually requires auth
3	AWS	150+	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	Documentation freely accessible; testing requires AWS account
4	Microsoft	100+	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	Public access to API definitions, examples, and documentation
5	IBM	80+	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	Browsable catalog; testing via API key requires login
6	Kong	100+	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	All APIs browsable without login; clear versioning and categorization
7	RapidAPI	10,000	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	Browsable catalog without login; testing requires registration
8	Oracle	n/a	<input type="checkbox"/> Partial	Documentation accessible, but lacks a dedicated public API catalog
9	Salesforce	n/a	<input type="checkbox"/> Partial	Documentation available, but not organized as a structured API catalog
10	MuleSoft	n/a	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Login required even to browse the catalog

Official Links

No.	Title (as Link)	Description
1	GraphQL.org	The official website of GraphQL, with learning materials, documentation, and community links.
2	GraphQL Spec on GitHub	The canonical specification for GraphQL, maintained via RFCs and Working Group decisions.
3	GraphQL Working Group	Meeting notes, RFC proposals, and process discussions for evolving the GraphQL spec.
4	GraphQL Foundation	Oversees the governance, community growth, and ecosystem of GraphQL. Under the Linux Foundation.

Awesome Repos

No.	Title (as Link)	Description
1	Awesome GraphQL by chentsulin	The most comprehensive list of GraphQL-related tools, servers, clients, and community resources. Covers multiple languages and layers of the stack.
2	Awesome GraphQL by caixie-team	A curated list of GraphQL libraries, developer tools, IDE integrations, and plugins. More tooling-focused.
3	Awesome React GraphQL by Hasura	Tailored for React and React Native developers integrating GraphQL. Includes tutorials, clients, and boilerplates.
4	Awesome Fluent GraphQL by Hasura	Highlights fluent API clients and examples for GraphQL. Useful for developers using strongly typed or declarative query building.
5	Awesome GraphQL Java by graphql-java	Focused on the Java ecosystem, including GraphQL libraries, frameworks (e.g. Spring), and tooling support.

Social Media & Community Channels

No.	Platform (as Link)	Description
1	Mastodon @graphql@mastodon.social	Official Mastodon account of the GraphQL Foundation.
2	Bluesky @graphql.org	Official Bluesky account of the GraphQL Foundation.
3	Matrix Room	Developer chat room for GraphQL topics, community-run.
4	YouTube – GraphQL Foundation	Official channel for Working Group meetings, conferences, and tutorials.